

Наука среди нас

Сетевое научно-практическое издание

№5(9) 2018

УДК 001
ББК 72

Наука среди нас : сетевое научно-практическое издание №5(9) / под ред. В.И. Вахрушева. – Магнитогорск : ИП Вахрушев В.И., 26.05.2018. – 794 с.

В журнале освещаются результаты исследований, актуальные вопросы, новости и события из мира науки.

Журнал зарегистрирован в Федеральной службе по надзору в сфере связи, информационных технологий и массовых коммуникаций.

Свидетельство о регистрации СМИ: ЭЛ № ФС 77 - 71150.

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THE WAYS OF TRANSLATING CULTURE-SPECIFIC WORDS FROM UZBEK INTO ENGLISH

Abstract: This article examines the methods of translating special cultural words from English into Uzbek. And also there are examples of various ways used in the learning process, their advantages and problems of translation.

Keywords: methods, aspect, classroom management, conversation, pupils, lesson, situation.

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ПУТИ ПЕРЕВОДА КУЛЬТУРНО-СПЕЦИФИЧЕСКИХ СЛОВ С УЗБЕКСКОГО НА АНГЛИЙСКИЙ

Аннотация: Данная статья рассматривает методы перевода специальных культурных слов с английского на узбекский язык. А также даны примеры различных способов используемых в процессе обучения, их преимущества и проблемы перевода.

Ключевые слова: методы, аспект, классное руководство, разговор, ученики, урок, ситуация.

Translation of culture-specific c references poses many translation problems when translating from one language into another one. Difficulties arise because languages have different grammatical structures. Furthermore, culture-specific references vary among cultures as various countries have a different history and experience of life. The term —non-equivalence could be explained as non-existence of a parallel concept or expression in the language of the other culture. As Mona Baker notes, -non-equivalence at word level means that the target language has no direct equivalent for a word which occurs in the source text.[1/20]

Culture-specific concepts are one of the types of non-equivalence. Culture-specific concepts may be -abstract or concrete; it may relate to a religious belief, a social custom, or even a type of food. In other words, the source text concepts may have no known meaning in the target language.[1/21]

Sometimes equivalent-lacking words are associated with culture-bound words, the Uzbek equivalent being реалиялар (derived from Latin realis, pl. realia), or culturally loaded words. However, the term of culture-bound word is of narrower meaning than the

term of equivalent-lacking word. A culture-bound word names an object peculiar to this or that ethnic culture (валенки, матрешка; baby shower, kimono, atlas, adras).

Equivalent-lacking words include, along with culture-bound words, neologisms, i.e. newly coined forms, dialect words, slang, taboo-words, foreign (third language) terms, proper names, misspellings, archaisms, etc.

In the process of translating —Alexander's wall into English translator is confronted with a great number of equivalent-lacking words such as, proper names, geographical names, archaisms and historical words. According to the semantic fields, culture-bound words in —Alexander's wall are classified into:

- toponyms, or geographical terms : Хоразм-Khorazm, Сирдарё-Syrdarya;
- anthroponyms, or people's names: Меҳрноз- Mehrnoz, Феруз- Feruz;
- social terms: Девонбеги -divanbegi (a man who is the chief of government office); Шох,Подшоҳ –Shah, Padishah;

- religious servants and rituals terms : Дарвеш – dervish (a man who lives lonely in wandering , doing good deeds to people);

Кофир -non-Muslim; Ҳизр -Hizr (one of the legendary prophet's name who is said to be immortal);

- clothing: тўппи,дўппи- duppi (embroidered scull-cap worn by men as well as women); зарбафтгўн -gold-brocaded robe; жубба – robe (outer clothing for common people); яланггўн -plain-robe (without any embroidered patterns and designs); дубулға -dubulgha (metal headdress, helmet); нимча -sleeveless jacket; ҳафтон -luxurious robe; ридо -religious garb шохпар -long feather (birds' long feather which were fastened on the men's headdresses);

- housing: карвонсарой –caravanserai (inn on the caravan route); ҳарам –harem (special building for shah's wives and children);

- Terms of measurement: Кари -kari (measurer of linear,one kari is equal to one metre); Ўйғоч -yigoch (measurer of linear,one yigoch is equal to 12.000 metres); Газ – gaz (unit of measurement of linear, equals approximately 105 cm);

Таноб – tanab (long string used for measuring the square, equals 63 metres);

- Terms of other things: Гўй – gouy (wooden ball); Чавгон – chavghan (a gouy-stick with its bent tip used for hitting the wooden ball, polo); Ганч –ganch (high quality plaster made largely from alabaster, often used for surface of sculpture);

Culture-bound words are characterized by a location and time. Based on the time coloring, they can be historical and archaic words. One couldn't find the translations of those words in modern bilingual dictionaries. Because the historical words are out of use and they don't have modern synonyms. As for archaic words, they aren't used anymore at present, but they have modern proper equivalents in use. In order to give their translations, translator should look up the monolingual definition dictionaries of SL. There are two ways of giving their translations:

To transform them into TL as realias;

In this way some translation techniques are required. The main ways of translating terms are as follows:

a) Transcription (for loan terms): хариса- harisa. Care should be taken not to overuse this technique. Terms may not survive in the borrowed form, as happened with the computer term hardware whose loan equivalent хардвер is no longer used in computer science, but has given way to its explanatory substitution: электромеханическое оборудование, техническое обеспечение.

b) Transliteration: Гўй – gouy, ҳарам –harem, карвонсарой –caravanserai. Normally, terms are transliterated or transcribed when a target language lacks a certain notion and borrows it a short foreign form.

However, when using this technique a translator should be aware of false friends, that is words similar in form but different in meaning, for example: Газ –gaz not natural gas, but it is measurement of linear.

c) Calque, half-calque: this technique is often applied to translating compound terms or term phrases: зарбафтгўн- gold-brocaded robe, яланггўн -plain-robe(without any embroidered patterns and designs). Transparent inner form of the word can cause no less trouble with translation equivalents: шоҳпар -long feather not king feather, яланггўн - plain-robe not naked-robe. [2/102]

In conclusion, it is necessary to underline that a translation can be defined as a double-phased process of interlinguistic and intercultural communication in which the secondary text represents the initial one in another cultural medium. Translation is also process-oriented towards a reconstruction of the communicative effect of the source text which takes into account the differences between cultures and two communicative situations.

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